

PROCEDURE FOR RECEIVING FOREIGN INVESTMENT AND SPENDING IT CORRECTLY

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Annotation: The main goal of investment reform is to further boost the economy through the development of production. This article explains how to attract foreign investment and how to spend it correctly.

Keywords: Investment, competition, network investment, export, import, strategy, investment activity.

Introduction

Since becoming independence, the Republic of Uzbekistan has been on the path of transition to a market economy. Investment policy is very important in this direction. Because the investment will stimulate structural changes in the economy, technical and technological innovations, the reconstruction of enterprises, increase the country's export and import potential. Investment policy is a set of measures taken in the region, which allows you to effectively use the investment, taking into account the interests of the population, region and investor. The sectoral investment policy is to support the development of the country's economy through the export of industrial products, the development of import-substituting industries, and the support of scientific and technological progress through investment.

Materials and methods

Investment is one of the elements of economic activity. Investment is

derived from the Latin word "investire", which means "investment". An investment is a long-term investment in a business or enterprise. The word investor is derived from the word investor - "depositor", which means the person, organization or state that makes the deposit. Investors include legal entities and individuals who buy securities and invest their own funds.

Real investment is all types of assets invested by investors in fixed assets and working capital. Financial investments are long-term investments in the purchase of securities (shares, bonds) and bank deposits. Intellectual investments - training, experience, research, licensing and know-how, copyright, etc.

Investments are divided into 2 types depending on who makes them:

1. Internal investment.
2. External investment.

Internal investment is an investment made by internal investors in the territory of the country. External investment is an investment made by external investors in the economy of another country for profit.

Results

The state structural investment policy pursues the following tasks in order to create and develop new industries, to achieve a high level of demand for consumer goods in the short term:

- gradual elimination of obsolete productions;
- support for local producers;
- creation of solvent and demand-driven production structures;
- ensuring the maximum possible use of production resources and scientific and technical potential;
- Ensuring and strengthening the environmental and economic security of the country;
- harmonizing the development of efficient, competitive industries, market infrastructure, services and intellectual activities;

- development of priority sectors of the economy and creation of new ones;
- increase employment and economic activity of the population;
- complete formation of social infrastructure of the regions.

Discussion

Important strategies have been developed for structural investment policy, the essence of which is to support the development of small economic entities. It is important to attract foreign investment in this work. Political stability in our country, a very favorable investment climate are the basis for foreign investors to create long-term investment projects. In addition, conditions are being created for the attraction of guarantees for foreign investment and loans, tax and customs tariff exemptions, interest rate subsidies, and dozens of legal documents are in force.

Forms of investment are:

- participation in the formation of legal entities or their shares in the charter funds (authorized capital), including through the purchase of property and shares (shares);
- Receipt of securities issued by residents of the Republic of Uzbekistan, including debt obligations;
- obtaining concessions, including concessions for the exploration, development, extraction or use of natural resources, as well as participation in product sharing agreements;
- property rights, including intellectual property rights, copyrights, patents, trademarks, utility models, industrial designs, trade names and know-how, business reputation (goodwill), as well as trade and services. Acquisition of property rights to the objects of the field of presentation together with the land plots on which they are located;

- ownership and use of land plots (including lease and use) and the right to own and use other natural resources.

Conclusion

The conclusion is that in the implementation of the state structural investment policy in the field, in rural areas, it is necessary to improve the gas, water, electricity, communications networks, to establish small enterprises on the basis of state benefits. This is the only way to attract foreign investment to agricultural enterprises.

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